

Microwave assisted synthesis of fungicidal compounds using Knoevenagel condensation in dry media

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An environmentally benign, solventless, rapid and economic technique for the synthesis of substituted quinolines, indoles and aromatic compounds using Knoevenagel condensation is described from readily available aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes and diethyl malonate on solid inorganic support under microwave irradiation (MWI). The method is devoid of the hazards of solution phase reactions. All the compounds are screened for their antifungal activity.

Ever since its discovery, the Knoevenagel condensation¹ catalyzed by a weak base has been widely applied in the elegant synthesis of fine chemicals². In the last few years, there is a growing interest for Knoevenagel products as many of them are pharmacologically active³. Various catalysts effect the Knoevenagel condensation either thermally or at room temperature in the presence of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ⁴, ZnCl_2 ⁵, BiCl_3 ⁶ etc. Several other methods include modified hydrotalcite/toluene⁷ and solid phase reactions⁸. Quinoline⁹ and indole¹⁰ derivatives are also well known for their significant biological activities. Though microwave energy in solution phase¹¹ has also been used to enhance the rate but this procedure is limited due to super-heating of the solvent which may lead to explosion ascribed to temperature and pressure effects¹². Consequently, there is a need for the development of newer methods which proceed under mild and environmentally benign conditions. The coupling of MWI with the use of solid supported reagents under solvent-free conditions¹³ provides a unique chemical processes with special attributes such as enhanced reaction rates, higher yields, greater selectivity and ease of manipulation.

In continuation of our growing interest¹⁴ in the development of economic, rapid and environmentally benign protocol, we now describe a microwave accelerated solid state approach for the synthesis of title compounds using Knoevenagel condensation on three different solid support, viz. basic alumina, montmorillonite K10 clay and silica gel.

Results and Discussion

Substituted aldehydes and diethyl malonate were condensed (Scheme 1) in the ratio of 1 : 3 respectively on solid inorganic support under MWI, afforded products (3a-i) which were evidenced by the appearance of signal at δ 7.6–

Scheme 1

7.95 for the vinylic proton in ¹H NMR spectra. In IR spectra, the disappearance of band C=O of CHO at 1695–1715 and appearance of bands due to C=O and OCH₂ of α,β -unsaturated ester at 1770–1790 and 1225–1260 cm^{-1} , respectively, confirm the product formation. The product formation was further confirmed by mass spectra. Conventional method¹⁵ with solid support in oil-bath maintained at 120° was also attempted but the reaction took 4.0–7.5 h to give the required products in 40–60% yields. The significance of our approach using solid support under MWI is that the condensation is completed in just 2–5 min with excellent yield, whereas in solution phase (MWI), the same reaction requires 7–12 min with lower yields. Furthermore, bases (K_2CO_3 /pyridine/piperidine etc.) used in the condensation reaction could cause undesired decarboxylation to give cinnamic acid analog, whereas in our approach, solid support (basic alumina, montmorillonite K10 clay) acts as catalyst as well as base thereby eliminating the usage of external base, solvents and noxious reagents originally used. Moreover, they also serve as water adsorbent and remove the water formed in the condensation whereas P_2O_5 was originally used to adsorb water.

The results (Table 1) reveal the versatility of the process as considerable enhancement of reaction rate has been observed by bringing down the reaction time from hours to seconds with improved yield as compared to conventional heating and also show that basic alumina is a better support in terms of yield and time for the synthesis of Knoevenagel condensation products as compared to montmorillonite K10 clay and silica gel. In conclusion, we have demonstrated a solvent-free environmentally benign methodology for the synthesis of bioactive compounds using Knoevenagel condensation under microwave irradiation and even the deactivated aldehydes¹⁶ (**1d**) gave excellent yield in a very short reaction time.

Antifungal activity : All the synthesized compounds were screened for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by paper-disc diffusion method¹⁷. Compounds were dissolved in DMF at concentrations 25 and 50 µg/ml. The zone of inhibition were measured in millimeters. The antifungal activity of test compounds was compared with salicyclic acid as standard¹⁸ (13–18 mm). The results of antifungal screening are as follows, all the compounds were found to be active. Compounds **3a-d** showed low activity (3–12 mm), **3e** moderate activity (10–

12 mm) and **3f-i** showed significant activity (13–21 mm) and were most potent comparable to salicyclic acid.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined using a Thomas-Hoover apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599 spectrophotometer model and PMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer operating at 90 MHz (δ in ppm) using TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel coated Al plates (Merck). Elemental analyses were performed on a Heracus CHN-rapid analyser. A Padmini Essentia microwave oven, Browine, at 2450 MHz was used for MWI (maximum power 750 W).

General procedure for the Synthesis of **3a-i** :

Method A. Solid phase conventional : To a solution of the aldehyde (**1a-i**; 0.01 mol) and diethyl malonate (0.03 mol) dissolved in acetone (10 ml), was added solid inorganic support with constant stirring. Adsorbed material was mixed properly, dried in air and heated in a oil-bath at 120–130° for 4.0–7.5 h. On completion of the reaction (TLC examination), the mixture was cooled to room temperature and the product was extracted into ethanol (4 × 15 ml). Removal of solvent under reduced pressure yielded the pure product.

Method B. Solution phase MWI : To a solution of the aldehydes (**1a-i**; 0.01 mol) and diethyl malonate (0.03 mol) dissolved in freshly distilled dry monochlorobenzene, were added K₂CO₃ (0.01 mol) and P₂O₅ (0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was then irradiated in a microwave oven for 7–12 min at medium power level (600 W) intermitently at 0.5 min intervals, at 120°. On completion of the reaction (TLC examination), the mixture was cooled to room temperature and diluted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer from insoluble materials was decanted and dried with MgSO₄. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure yielded the pure product.

Method C. Solid phase MWI : To a solution of the aldehyde (**1a-i**; 0.01 mol) and diethyl malonate (0.03 mole) dissolved in acetone (10 ml), was added solid inorganic support with constant stirring. Adsorbed material was mixed properly, dried in air (breaker) and placed in an alumina bath¹⁹ inside the microwave oven for 2–3 min at medium power level (600 W) intermitently at 0.5 min intervals, at 120°. On completion of reaction (TLC examination), the mixture was cooled to room temperature and then product was extracted into ethanol (4 × 15 ml). Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded the pure products : **3a**,

Table 1. Physical data of compounds **3a-i***

Compd. no.	Reaction time/(yield%)		
	Method A ^{a,b,c} h	Method B min	Method C s
3a	4/5/7 (60/50/40)	7 (70)	2/3/7 (92/89/80)
b	5/5.5/6.5 (55/52/42)	10 (72)	2.5/3.5/6/5 (91/87/82)
c	4/6/6 (59/53/40)	9 (75)	3/4/6 (90/85/80)
d	4.5/5/7.5 (58/50/45)	12 (76)	2.5/4/7 (91/89/78)
e	5/5.5/7 (60/49/45)	10 (74)	3/3.5/7 (93/84/75)
f	4.5/6/7 (59/51/47)	9 (79)	2/4/6.5 (95/86/84)
g	4/5.5/7.5 (60/55/41)	8.5 (76)	3/4/6.5 (90/82/82)
h	4.5/4.5/6/5 (59/56/40)	7.5 (78)	2/3/7 (95/90/78)
i	5/5/6.5 (60/49/43)	11.5 (73)	2.5/3.5/7 (93/85/75)

^aBasic alumina, ^bmontmorillonite K10 clay, ^csilica gel.

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

m.p. 70–72°, δ 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.35 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 3.15 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 4.26 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.36 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.82 (1H, s, vinyl-H), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 291 (291); **b**, 56–58°, δ 1.24 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.38 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.34 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.46 (4H, m, ArH), 7.80 (1H, s, vinyl-H), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 283 (282); **c**, 130–132°, δ 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.36 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.37 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.48 (4H, m, ArH), 7.89 (1H, s, vinyl-H), 10.1 (1H, s, OH), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 265 (264); **d**, 85–87°, δ 1.29 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.37 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.29 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.38 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 7.90 (1H, s, vinyl-H), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 292 (293); **e**, 94–96°, δ 1.27 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.35 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.25 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.35 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.91 (1H, s, vinyl-H), 8.8 (1H, b s, NH), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 286 (287); **f**, 60–62°, δ 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.37 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.48 (4H, m, ArH), 7.87 (1H, s, vinyl-H), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 333 (332); **g**, 57–59°, δ 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 3.7 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.27 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.38 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.47 (3H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, s, vinyl-H), 3.3 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 347 (347); **h**, 100–102°, δ 1.25 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 3.9 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.27 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.39 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 7.88 (1H, s, vinyl-H), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 318 (317); **i**, 140–142°, δ 1.29 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 4.38 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂), 7.51 (4H, m, ArH), 7.89 (1H, s, vinyl-H), 3.5 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), m/z M⁺ observed (expected) 331 (331).

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References

1. E. Knoevenagel, *Chem Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 738.
2. G. Johnes, *Org. React.*, 1967, **15**, 204.
3. J. D. Elliott and D. L. Bryan, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1997, **126**, 225309.
4. J. A. Cabello, J. M. Campelo, A. Carcia, D. Luna and J. M. Masinas, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, **49**, 4194.
5. D. Prajapati and J. S. Sandhu, *Chem. Lett.*, 1972, 1945.
6. F. Delgado, J. Tamari, G. Zepeda, M. Landa, R. Miranda and J. Grascia, *Synth. Commun.*, 1995, **25**, 753.
7. M. L. Kantam, B. M. Choudary, C. V. Reddy, K. K. Rao and F. Figueras, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 1033.
8. B. C. Hampes, S. A. Kolodziej and A. M. Scates, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, **391**, 2047.
9. D. R. Sidler, J. W. Sager, J. J. Bergan, K. M. Wells, M. Bhupasthy and R. P. Volante, *Tetrahedron Assym.*, 1997, **8**, 161; M. Kidwai, N. Negi and S. R. Chowdhury, *Acta Pharm.*, 1994, **45**, 511.
10. M. Kidwai, N. Negi and S. Kohli, *Acta Pharm.*, 1997, **47**, 53.
11. J. K. Kim, P. S. Kwon, T. W. Kwon, S. K. Chung and J. W. Lee, *Synth. Commun.*, 1996, **26**, 535.
12. R. Gedye, T. L. Bray, S. M. Duncan and G. Majetich, *Tetrahedron*, 1906, **27**, 4945.
13. D. C. Dittmer, *Chem. Ind.*, 1997, 779; I. Almena, E. Diez-Barra, A. Hoz, J. Ruiz and A. Sanchez-Migallon, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1998, **35**, 1263.
14. M. Kidwai, P. Sapra and B. Dave, *Synth. Commun.*, 2000, **30**, 4479; M. Kidwai, K. R. Bhusan and P. Sapra, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **8**, 69; M. Kidwai, N. Negi and P. Misra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 46.
15. G. Bram and G. Decordts, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, **21**, 5011.
16. Substituted aromatic heterocyclic ketones also undergo Knoevenagel condensation in similar reaction condition as reported in literature (P. de la Cruz, E. D. Barra, A. Loupy and F. Langa, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 1113).
17. H. W. Seeley and P. J. Van Denmark, "Microbes in Action", Freeman WH & Co, 1972.
18. F. Knvessel and F. G. Weirich, *Dermatologia*, 1972, **145**, 233; Clotrimazole was not used as a standard drug as it is not easily available in pure form, marketed along with additives; on the other hand, salicylic acid is well known to show activity against diverse fungal strains.
19. G. Bram, A. Loupy and M. Majoub, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **46**, 5167.